

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 117

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 117

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 117:1 "Praise the LORD, all nations; Laud Him, all peoples! ² For His "lovingkindness ¹is great toward us, And the ^{2b}truth of the LORD is everlasting. ³Praise ⁴the LORD!</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 117:1 הִלְלוּ אֶת־יְהוָה כָּל־גּוֹיִם שִׁבְחוּהוּ כָּל־הָאֲמִיּוֹת : ² כִּי יִגְבַּר עָלֵינוּ אֱמֶת־יְהוָה לְעוֹלָם הִלְלוּ־יְהוָה :</p>

References

Psalm 117:1

^aRom 15:11

Psalm 117:2

¹Lit *prevails over us*

²Or *faithfulness*

³Or *Hallelujah!*

⁴Heb *YAH*

^aPs 103:11

^bPs 100:5; 146:6

Targum

Psa. 117:1 Praise the LORD, all you Gentiles; praise him, all you nations. ² For he has increased his goodness towards us; and the truth of the LORD is forever. Hallelujah!

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

The Sage Radak said that the brevity of the Psalm symbolizes the simplicity of the world order when the Messiah comes. In the future, there will be two groups of people: the Children of Israel who follow Torah and the rest who follow the Torah's seven Noachide laws.

“The 7 Noahide Laws are rules that all of us must keep, regardless of who we are or from where we come. Without these seven things, it would be impossible for humanity to live together in harmony.

1. **Do not profane G-d's Oneness in any way.**

Acknowledge that there is a single [G-d](#) who cares about what we are doing and desires that we take care of His world.

2. **Do not curse your Creator.**

No matter how angry you may be, do not take it out verbally against your Creator.

3. **Do not murder.**

The value of human life cannot be measured. To destroy a single human life is to destroy the entire world—because, for that person, the world has ceased to exist. It follows that by sustaining a single human life, you are sustaining an entire universe.

4. **Do not eat a limb of a still-living animal.**

Respect the life of all G-d's creatures. As intelligent beings, we have a duty not to cause undue pain to other creatures.

5. **Do not steal.**

Whatever benefits you receive in this world, make sure that none of them are at the unfair expense of someone else.

6. **Harness and channel the human libido.**

Incest, adultery, rape and homosexual relations are forbidden. The family unit is the foundation of human society. Sexuality is the fountain of life and so nothing is more holy than the sexual act. So, too, when abused, nothing can be more debasing and destructive to the human being.

7. **Establish courts of law and ensure justice in our world.**

With every small act of justice, we are restoring harmony to our world, synchronizing it with a supernal order. That is why we must keep the laws established by our government for the country's stability and harmony.

These laws were communicated by G-d to Adam and Noah, ancestors of all human beings. That is what makes these rules universal, for all times, places and people:

Laws made by humans may change according to circumstance. But laws made by the Creator of all souls over all of time remain the same for all people at all times..

If we would fulfill these laws just because they make sense to us, then we would change them, according to our convenience. We would be our own god. But when we understand that they are the laws of a supreme G-d, we understand that they can not be changed, just as He does not change.”¹

¹ “The 7 Noahide Laws: Universal Morality - Chabad.org,” accessed February 17, 2023, https://www.chabad.org/library/article_cdo/aid/62221/jewish/The-7-Noahide-Laws-Universal-Morality.htm.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

